

CECILIA COSTA

ROBUST LOCAL POPULATIONS: LESSONS LEARNED

Robustezza delle popolazioni locali: evidenze acquisite

Many beekeepers report that honey bee colonies of local origin seem to survive longer and with an overall general better health status and balance with the environment compared to colonies with queens bought from elsewhere. These anecdotal reports are found across the current range of *Apis mellifera*, for many different subspecies.

A study on the Italian *A. m. ligustica* provided evidence for the existence of Genotype by Environment Interactions (GxE): three subpopulations of *A. m. ligustica* were exchanged across the three environments of origin, and the spring development and honey production of the colonies were monitored as indicators for local adaptation. It was found that in most cases colonies had better spring development and nectar collection in the location where they were native (COSTA *et al.*, 2012). A similar study on two genotypes of *A. m. carnica* of continental and alpine origin also found significant G x E for colony development (DRAZIC *et al.*, 2013).

Within the COLOSS COST Action for “Prevention of honey bee colony losses” a working group dedicated to investigating the role of diversity and vitality on colony health was set up in 2008, and in 2009 a pan European experiment was started to investigate the role of genetic origin on colony losses. More specifically, the aim of the study was to investigate the effects of genotype-environment interactions on the survival, performance and disease susceptibility of honey bee colonies headed by queens originating from several areas in Europe and tested in various locations under differing environmental conditions and in conditions

of high *Varroa* infestation - no chemical treatments for *Varroa* were enacted. 16 different genotypes from different backgrounds were included: some from breeding programs with strong focus on specific traits, others from conservation programs with little selection. The 16 genotypes were located in 21 locations in 11 countries across Europe. In each location the local strain was tested together with at least 2 other strains of different origin. Of the observed colonies, 16% survived until the end of the observation period. A survival analysis showed highly significant effects of the test location, the genotype and the origin of queen (local vs. non-local) on the longevity of colonies. Colonies of local origin survived on average 80 days more than colonies of non-local origin (BÜCHLER *et al.*, 2014). Other measured traits showed high variability among genotypes and locations. Overall, this experiment showed that there is a high diversity of bee populations in Europe, which can ensure a high genetic adaptability of European honey bee populations. Furthermore, the results of the study show that it is not merely an ecological issue, but also a commercial one: the use of local honey bee populations provides a higher chance of colony survival.

More recently, a pilot study funded by the European Commission: EurBeST also highlighted the existence of G x E in many honey bee strains for most traits and how colonies of local origin tendentially have better overall performance. Thus, local breeding activities should be promoted and encouraged throughout the native range of *Apis mellifera*.

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REFERENCES

- BÜCHLER R., COSTA C., HATJINA F., ANDONOV S., MEIXNER M.D., LE CONTE Y., UZUNOV A., BERG S., BIENKOWSKA M., BOUGA M., DRAZIC M., DYRBA W., KRYGER P., PANASIUK B., PECHHACKER H., PETROV P., KEZIC N., KORPELA S. & WILDE J., 2014. The influence of genetic origin and its interaction with environmental effects on the survival of *Apis mellifera* L. colonies in Europe. *J. Apicul. Res.*, 53(2): 205- 214.
- COSTA C., LODESANI M. & BIENEFELD K., 2012. Differences in colony phenotypes across different origins and locations: evidence for genotype by environment interactions in the Italian honeybee (*Apis mellifera ligustica*)? *Apidologie*, 43 (6): 634-642.
- DRAŽIĆ M. M., FILIPI J., PRĐUN S., BUBALO D., ŠPEHAR M., CVITKOVIĆ D., KEZIĆ D., PECHHACKER H. & KEZIĆ N., 2014. Colony development of two Carniolan genotypes (*Apis mellifera carnica*) in relation to environment. *J. Apicul. Res.*, 53(2): 261-268.

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